

Bringing EOSC Task Force Outcomes to the Austrian RDM Community

Date: 7 October 2024

Time: 13 – 14:30

Location: online, via Zoom

Attendees: 34 (highest number reached)

Agenda

- Welcome and introduction of event
- Input Speaker 1: Tereza Kalová, University of Vienna- TF Data Stewardship, Curricula & Career Paths
- Input speaker 2: Miguel Rey Mazón, TU Graz- TF Financial Sustainability
- Open Discussion between attendees and speakers

Welcome and introduction of the event

Outcomes from the Task Forces will be discussed with the community.

Input Speaker 1: Tereza Kalová, University of Vienna – TF Data Stewardship, Curricula & Career Paths

This task force operated from 2022-2023 with 24 members from 18 European countries. The group comprised stakeholders from universities, national/international organizations, and projects like Skills4EOSC and CLARIAH and BBMRI-ERIC.

The focus was on data stewards, their roles, training, and the international alignment of their curricula. Collaborations included professionalizing data stewardship, addressing training and career paths. Two distinct workstreams were created: one on curricula and another on career paths.

A comprehensive report with numerous recommendations for stakeholders was published, building on existing work in data stewardship skills and training. Key contributions came from Austria's FAIR Data Austria project and the data certificate program at the University of Vienna.

For the second workstream on career paths, desk research was conducted, and five key recommendations were made, mostly for the EOSC Association and related projects. The task force also advised the EOSC board, enhancing the positioning of data stewardship in strategic plans like the SRIA and the multi-annual roadmap.

Key Recommendations:

1. Policymakers: Harmonize data stewardship competencies and hiring processes across Europe and internationally, supporting more aligned curricula. Investment is needed for advanced education and professionalization of data stewardship roles, including accredited and domain-specific training.

2. **Accredited Training:** Emphasize the importance of certified, formal training through recognized universities. Shift from short-term courses to accredited programs that provide formal recognition.
3. **Core Curricula in Degree Programs:** Integrate data stewardship and research data management skills into all degree programs across disciplines.
4. **Research Performing Organizations (RPOs):** Encourage commitment to the education of data stewards in institutional strategies. Include both technical and soft skills in training programs.

The second part on career paths for data stewards was discussed, highlighting the lack of research in this area. While institutions focus on recruiting, hiring, and training data stewards, the critical question is what comes next after they have served in the role for several years. There is a significant need to establish clear career progression paths that allow data stewards to develop and advance within institutions.

The task force's recommendations for career paths include:

1. **Permanent Expert Group:** Establish a permanent expert group on data stewardship to advise the EOSC Association and related projects.
2. **Online Inventory:** Create an online inventory of various data steward initiatives.
3. **Professional Network:** Assess the need for a professional network for data stewards in Europe.

Input Speaker 2: Miguel Rey Mazón, TU Graz – TF Financial Sustainability

It was reflected on the work and outcomes of the Financial Sustainability Task Force. The group was composed of diverse experts in policies, funding, RDM, and legal aspects, including strong representation from Austrian institutions like AUSSDA and Open Knowledge Maps. The task force managed to navigate the extensive literature on sustainability and funding, ensuring their findings were well-received by the community.

Key timeline and outcomes:

1. **Formation and Direction:** The task force started in November 2021. The first year focused on defining tasks and approach, leading to an interim report before the 2022 EOSC symposium in Prague.
2. **Community Consultation:** A consultation process followed in early 2023, analyzing feedback and discussions during the 2023 symposium.
3. **Final Report:** After receiving input from the community, the final report was completed in late 2023 and published in April 2024.

The task force's mandate was to provide tangible proposals for financial sustainability for EOSC, rather than focusing on business models. Their work built on the foundation of the Fair Daily Report (2020) and the concept of a "minimal viable EOSC," consisting of core functions, services in the EOSC Exchange, and the yet-to-be-designed Data Federation.

The outcomes of the Financial Sustainability Task Force and their recommendations for a financially sustainable EOSC post-2027 were discussed. Despite challenges in determining a clear final product, the task force produced a report containing eight key principles and several additional issues that should guide the sustainable financing of EOSC.

Key points:

1. Eight Principles for Financial Sustainability:

- Agreement between the European Commission and member states on funding is essential for long-term sustainability.
- Coordination is crucial to avoid duplication of existing infrastructures.
- Access to services must be guaranteed for the community, with increased usage costs covered by member states.
- A clear governance and legal structure must be agreed upon, supported by key stakeholders.
- Utilizing existing services developed by researchers for researchers will maximize investment efficiency.
- Barriers for countries to participate in EOSC should be minimized, keeping costs low to encourage broad participation.

2. Additional Issues:

- Address cost recovery mechanisms and the role of commercial services in EOSC.
- Resolve legal aspects such as procurement and VAT.
- Consider non-technical costs to ensure a consistent approach to financing EOSC.

The task force's work aimed to provide tangible recommendations while avoiding overly specific prescriptions or business models. The focus was on high-level principles rather than detailed financial models, given the evolving nature of the EOSC landscape.

While much has been achieved, many questions remain unanswered, particularly around funding and sustainability of the EOSC beyond 2027.

Key points:

1. Final Calculations and the "Helicopter View":

- An estimate was provided for the financial resources needed to sustain the core of the EOSC federation, with figures ranging from €10 million to €50 million per year. These estimates were based on known procurement figures for EOSC and reflect realistic assumptions on service management.
- The EOSC Exchange services are expected to operate independently of EC funding, which simplifies financial planning for the core federation.

- Comparisons were made to earlier estimates on the cost of not having fair data, which run into the hundreds of millions of euros, suggesting that the EOSC budget, though substantial, is justified.

2. Current Outlook:

- The EOSC Federation is taking shape, with ongoing discussions about which organizations will become EOSC nodes.
- The sustainability conversation will continue until the conclusion of the Horizon Europe program, with major decisions on the future of EOSC expected before FP10 starts in 2027.
- The task force's work is complete, but the issue of sustainability remains unresolved. Their report serves as a foundation for future discussions and planning.

The full report is available on the EOSC website for those interested in further details.

Open Discussion between attendees and speakers

- What are the next steps for the task force's recommendations on data stewardship. Specifically, what Tereza expects or ideally hopes will happen at the national or institutional level with the recommendations they produced.
 - Hope was expressed that institutions engaged with the EOSC activities will seriously consider and implement the recommendations from the task force. She noted that some individuals involved in developing the recommendations are already beginning to apply them within their institutions and discussions, particularly regarding curricula and career paths.
Regarding curricula, there's an increasing awareness of available training opportunities, leading to more collaboration among training initiatives. However, discussions about sustainable career paths for data stewards are just beginning across Europe, as the role has not been established long enough for many to have extensive experience (no data stewards have held that title for more than ten years).
The need for institutions to consider career progression options for data stewards beyond typical management roles was emphasized, possibly inspired by industry practices, to create expert career tracks that offer recognition, better titles, and improved compensation for those in specialized roles.
- Could the EOSC SOA take on a coordinating role for training initiatives?
 - Currently this is not feasible due to concerns regarding financial sustainability. The Support Office aims to facilitate conversations among the various training initiatives and promote them within the community, but it cannot assume a more formal coordinating or managerial role at this time. National programs and alignment of activities, as seen in Germany, could serve as valuable examples for Austria. This kind of national framework is not yet fully developed in Austria.
- The interest in increasing the coordination among Austrian institutions engaged in Data Stewardship was expressed. The University of Graz has a Data Stewards Training program,

partially modeled after the one in Vienna, though with some differences. CLARIAH supports early-stage researchers, including funding for data steward certification.

The value of closer collaboration and possibly harmonizing curricula between Graz and Vienna, while maintaining unique focuses was mentioned. This coordination could also extend within the CLARIAH context, particularly involving cultural heritage institutions, whose needs often align with research institutions.

- Will there be opportunities for task forces to present results or discuss next steps?
 - The response indicated that no such presentations are currently planned, but attendees involved in task forces will be present for discussions if needed.
 - Clarification was provided that these topics are primarily related to the upcoming EOSC Gravity project, a continuation of EOSC Focus. Discussions on sustainability remain relevant, especially concerning the federation of nodes.
 - It was noted that entities aspiring to become nodes will need to provide their own resources, as there is limited funding available from the European Commission during the build-up phase of the federation.
 - The *Long-term Data Retention Task Force* will use the Berlin meeting for a face-to-face meeting, as they have only had virtual meetings so far. This task force is newly formed, and while there may not be a formal presentation at the symposium, they are using the opportunity to gather in person.

- Gratitude for the productive work of the task forces and raised concerns about funding, particularly regarding the federation architecture and public sector contributions was expressed. It was noted that significant funds have already been spent by institutions like CERN and other research infrastructures. The speaker highlighted the co-programmed partnership model as beneficial, referencing a report that showed EOSC as the best-financed partnership, even over-financed, due to Europe-wide measures. The future funding of EOSC efforts were emphasized. Member states on the steering board hold differing views on the funding model and architecture.

A major concern raised was the considerable amount of money spent so far (approximately €1 billion) compared to the original estimate of €5 million from 2018. Questions are being asked about how this money has been used, though the speaker acknowledged that the results have been positive, particularly within the scientific community.

The speaker stressed the increasing costs of research infrastructures and data services, presenting an ongoing challenge. They concluded by requesting the presentation for further discussions.

 - There are concerns about the European Commission's intention to shift costs for national nodes to member states, and these financial considerations must account for the current economic climate, including wars and energy costs. It was emphasized that EOSC remains a priority in the European Research Area, and discussions involving member states and the scientific community demonstrate the critical mass driving these efforts. However, there are concerns about some parts of the European Commission (such as DG Connect) showing neglect toward EOSC. The EU Node of EOSC is expected to launch soon, offering essential services like computing hours and storage, which will

address practical needs in fields like high-energy physics. While the node is a positive step, further efforts are needed to build a complete federation of services. Resources are necessary to ensure EOSC's success, as the work relies on both people and machines. AI for science initiatives, including AI factories that could be developed within the EOSC framework, potentially supported by the EuroHPC initiative.

- A question was posed to the speakers regarding experiences with task forces, particularly asking for pitfalls to avoid. The speaker, as a member of a new task force, sought advice on how to ensure clarity in defining the task force's purpose and output.
 - It is a voluntary role and can be challenging to prioritize amidst other commitments. They shared experiences from the Data Stewardship Task Force, where only about half of the 24 members were actively engaged, while others participated sporadically or eventually disengaged ("ghosted"). This is a common frustration in voluntary groups. Key advice for newcomers: active participation leads to better outcomes, both in terms of task force results and professional networking. The speaker emphasized the long-term benefits, such as continued collaboration and building relationships. A challenge highlighted was the tight deadlines from the EOSC Association, which often asked for feedback on large documents within short timeframes. The speaker encouraged members to contribute when possible but not to feel discouraged if they can't always meet the deadlines, as more opportunities will arise.
 - The active engagement of their task force was discussed, emphasizing that direct conversations with the EOSC Association Board were highly beneficial. The importance of obtaining a concrete mandate from the EOSC Association to avoid ambiguity in the task force's objectives. Clear direction helps prevent impractical tasks and allows for refinement as the environment changes. Maintaining an open and direct dialogue with the Association Board while staying flexible to adjust approaches as needed is recommended. While keeping the board happy is important, delivering the best outcome—even if it diverges from the initial plan—should be the goal.
- How were the recommendations developed from the TF Financial Sustainability?
 - It was explained that their process involved a combination of literature review, community engagement, and consultations with relevant stakeholders, including the EOSC Association, the European Commission, and member states. An interim report with preliminary recommendations was followed by a community survey in early 2023, which helped refine the final recommendations. The recommendations were based on practicality and feasibility, though their implementation may require adjustments, political will, and funding, which remain uncertain.